

Review

Restoring fire regimes through rewilding

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SUMMARY

Accelerating anthropogenic changes to climate and landscapes have degraded ecosystems globally; these include changes to naturally occurring disturbances, such as fires. Rewilding — the restoration of ecological processes to yield complex and resilient ecosystems — is a proposed strategy to maintain biodiversity in increasingly novel systems. Fire is one important ecological process in many ecosystems around the world. However, substantial changes to fire patterns are now threatening ecosystems. Pathways for how rewilding can be used to restore fire regimes have yet to be explored. Here, we illustrate how fire regimes could be restored through rewilding, benefiting biodiversity and ecosystem resilience. First, we review how fire regimes have been altered due to anthropogenic pressures. Second, we show how fire interacts with other key ecological processes included in the rewilding framework, in particular dispersal and trophic complexity. Third, we showcase approaches to defining restored fire regimes in the context of rewilding. Fourth, we outline a general pathway to restoring fire regimes with rewilding and provide examples of rewilding actions that account for different socio-ecological contexts. Lastly, we highlight some important challenges and opportunities for rewilding in restoring fire regimes to enhance ecological function in a novel biosphere.

Introduction

A combination of changes in land-use, climate and disturbance regimes has led to unprecedented levels of ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss^{1,2}. Intensification of human-driven disturbances in recent decades³ and associated ecological novelty and declines in ecosystem function demonstrate that current efforts to protect and restore ecosystems must scale up, and that innovative approaches are required⁴. One such approach is rewilding, which focuses on restoring the ecological processes that promote complex and resilient ecosystems^{5–7}. Rewilding differs from traditional restoration ecology, as it does not aim to recreate clearly defined end-states based on historical species assemblages^{5,8,9}.

Instead, rewilding aims to restore three interacting ecological processes — trophic complexity, dispersal and disturbance — with the aim of restoring functioning, self-sustaining socio-ecological ecosystems, inclusive of people (Box 1)^{10,11}. Rewilding, as we define here, does not seek to recover ‘wilderness’ to a benchmark state before human existence but recognizes the important role of people in ecological processes¹². Rewilding is a collaboration between people and other beings to restore ecological agency of all beings, recover ecological processes¹³, and in relation, to progress towards more complex, resilient, and

functioning ecosystems. We acknowledge there are important unresolved discussions on the term ‘rewilding’ and its capacity for inclusion^{13–16}. We suggest that these important ongoing discussions should not obscure the core focus of the present review, which is to understand and restore fire within a network of ecological processes, critical to fostering sustainable ecosystems in a time of global change. Identifying what constitutes these ecological processes, how they have been altered, and how rewilding actions may restore them is essential to understand the possibilities of promoting complex, functioning ecosystems.

Fire is an important disturbance and many ecosystems have evolved with and are regulated by fire^{17,18}. Many species in fire-prone environments display adaptations dating back to the mid-Cretaceous that enable their population persistence (Box 1)¹⁹. For example, 66% of plants in the Brazilian Cerrado flower stimulated by fire²⁰. Animals may also depend on fire, primarily through the influence of fire on the environment. For example, Northern Betong (*Bettongia tropica*), a marsupial in tropical open forests of Northern Australia, experience population declines in the absence of fire, driven by the reduction of the key food resource Cockatoo Grass (*Alloternopsis semialata*)²¹. Fire can also promote animal dispersal, such as by attracting grazing

Box 1. Glossary.

Rewilding	We adopt definitions from ¹⁰ and ¹³ , to focus on restoring ecological processes of trophic complexity, disturbance, and dispersal, as a partnership between people and other beings, with the goal of restoring functioning, self-sustaining socio-ecological systems.
Trophic complexity	The taxonomic and functional composition of the consumer community, along with the number and diversity of trophic interactions, i.e. between trophic levels ¹¹ .
Dispersal	The movement of individuals within the landscape, and at a population level the exchange and mixing of individuals. Dispersal is facilitated by habitat connectivity ¹² .
Disturbance regimes	The size, magnitude and spatial arrangements of disturbance events, such as fire, storms, drought and pests, and their timing and frequency ¹² . Disturbances are implicitly different within different landscapes. The spatial footprints of disturbance events are themselves heterogenous and the recurrence of disturbance events over time forms still more complex and heterogenous spatial patterns.
Fire-prone ecosystems	Environments that have a long evolutionary history with fire. This contrasts with systems in which fire has been introduced as a contemporary condition but have not evolved with fire.
Fire-sensitive ecosystems	Environments that have no or limited evolutionary history with fire. These ecosystems may have experienced contemporary introductions of fire.
Novel ecosystems	Self-developing ecosystems with a changed biotic assemblage and abiotic structure from a distinct historical baseline ²⁰⁵ .

animals that forage on young shoots of recently burnt grasses^{22,23}. At a community level, the passage of fire can enable the renewal of entire forest stands, such as in North American Lodgepole pine forests (*Pinus contorta* var. *latifolia*), where periodic stand-replacing fire produces important variability in species assemblages, forest structure and function for decades to centuries^{24,25}. Across many ecosystems, variation in fire patterns creates ecological niches for different species²⁶, balancing competition among species that have different responses to fire^{27,28}. Fire therefore plays a crucial role at the population level, at the community level, but also at the biome level²⁹, mediating competition, creating ecological niches, and facilitating diverse landscape patterns.

While people have used fire to shape complex and resilient ecosystems for millennia^{30,31}, recent human pressure has altered fire patterns³². Particularly for the last two hundred years, anthropogenic changes in climate, land-use, biotic mixing and fire application and suppression have altered fire frequency and its spatial configuration^{33–36}. As part of these alterations, people have introduced fire to fire-sensitive ecosystems that have not evolved with fire, particularly tropical and wet temperate forests (Box 1). For example, in the tropical forests of Vietnam, human population growth has led to a large increase in fire ignitions³⁷. This can cause positive feedbacks that lead to alternative stable states³⁸. In some fire-prone ecosystems (Box 1), recent anthropogenic actions have increased the energetic intensity of fire, its frequency and lengthened the season in which fires burn. For example, large-scale, monoculture plantations of highly flammable *Eucalyptus* spp. and *Pinus* spp. have contributed to increased fire size and intensity in Chile and Portugal^{39,40}. Similarly, in the fire-prone Eurasian Steppe, urbanization and abandonment of agricultural lands have increased the total area burnt per year⁴¹. Increased fire outside the natural fire season can cause mismatches between fire and species' capacities to persist, even for fire-adapted species⁴².

Conversely, in other fire-prone systems, particularly savannas and grasslands, intensive human input has decreased fire

frequency, due to reduced fuel availability from increases in livestock density and habitat fragmentation^{43,44}. Likewise, exclusion of Indigenous burning practices and increased fire suppression have lowered the frequency of low-intensity fires, yet increased the severity of infrequent fires⁴⁵. Such fire exclusion can result in biome shifts, with associated turnover in species composition and functioning^{46,47}. These novel anthropogenic patterns of fire are thus degrading ecosystems and their characteristic biota, posing a risk to the ecosystem services on which humans rely, as well as human lives and property.

Rewilding can help to recover essential and dynamic ecological processes, benefiting biodiversity, ecosystem function and human well-being⁴⁸. In this review, we aim to demonstrate how rewilding may progress towards the restoration of fire regimes to safeguard biodiversity and ecosystem functioning. We discuss ways in which fire regimes have been altered, and how fire interacts with other ecological processes, outline a general pathway to restoring fire regimes and discuss examples of rewilding in various socio-ecological contexts.

Fire regimes

Fire events can be quantified by energetic or spatial characteristics, such as how energetically intense the fire is, the impact of that intensity on biota, i.e. its severity, and the fire's size and patchiness³⁴. These fire events can be understood in the context of fire patterns over time, forming the "fire regime", characterized by the frequency or interval of fire events, the time of year that they burn (season), and their complex spatial arrangements⁴⁹. Many species have adapted to particular kinds of fire regimes, comprising specific types of fire events and their temporal patterns⁵⁰.

There are four 'switches'⁵¹ needed to create a fire event: fuel availability — the vegetative biomass present across the ground, shrub and canopy layers; fuel dryness, related primarily to the recent climate and precipitation that an area has experienced; an ignition source, such as lightning strikes or human ignition;

Table 1. Anthropogenic changes to fire regimes.

Intensive anthropogenic influence	Fire switch	Types of impacts on fire regime
Climate change	Fuel dryness: decrease in fuel moisture content ⁵⁷ Fire weather: increase in number of days of fire weather ⁶⁰ Suppression: decrease in efficacy of suppression actions ⁵⁹	Increase in frequency of large, uniform and severe wildfires ³⁶
Fire suppression	Suppression: of active small fires ⁶³ Fuel availability: build up in suppressed areas ⁶³	Reduction in frequency of small fires ⁶³ Increase in frequency of large, uniform and severe wildfires ⁶³
Urbanization	Ignition source: increases in accidental ignition ²⁰⁶ Fuel availability: reduction in fuel connectivity, due to housing and infrastructure ²⁰⁷ Suppression: protection of life and assets ⁶⁴	Increase in fire frequency ²⁰⁶ Decrease in fire frequency and fire size ^{207,208}
Land abandonment	Fuel availability: increased fuel availability as rural land no longer used for agriculture ⁷⁵	Increase in frequency of large, uniform, and severe fires ^{76,78}
Colonization driven exclusion of people	Ignition source: exclusion of or reduction in human ignition sources ⁶⁵ Fuel availability: build-up of fuel in areas where fire excluded ¹⁴⁵	Reduction in frequency of small, heterogenous fires ⁶⁵ Increase in large, uniform, and severe wildfires ¹⁴⁵
Plantation forestry	Fuel availability: increase in connectedness of fuel and type of species/flammability of species ³⁹	Increase in frequency of large, contiguous, severe wildfires ³⁹
Conflict and war	Ignition source: increase in ignitions due to weaponry ²⁰⁹	Increase in fire frequency ²⁰⁹
Land conversion to agriculture	Fuel availability: decreased connectivity due to fragmentation ²¹⁰ Ignitions: increased ignitions due to burning to clear forest for pasture and croplands ¹⁷⁵	Decrease in fire frequency ²¹⁰ Increase in fire frequency and size ⁶⁸
Forest logging	Fuel availability: decreased connectivity ²¹¹ Fuel dryness: decrease in fuel moisture content ²¹³	Decrease in fire frequency, intensity and size ²¹² Increase in fire frequency and size ²¹⁴
Herding or grazing	Fuel availability: decreased fuel load and connectivity due to herbivory ²¹⁵	Decrease in fire frequency and size ²¹⁵
Hydrological interventions	Fuel dryness: decrease in fuel moisture content ²¹⁶	Increase in fire frequency and size ²¹⁷
Plant introductions	Fuel availability: changes to flammability and structure of species assemblages ¹⁰⁹	Increase in fire intensity, decrease or increase in fire frequency ¹⁰⁹
Herbivore removals or extinctions	Fuel availability: increase in fuel load and connectivity due to herbivore extinctions ¹¹⁴	Increase in frequency of large, contiguous, severe wildfires ¹¹⁴

and fire weather — hot, dry and windy conditions that carry a fire across the landscape⁵¹. These four switches are determined by environmental conditions and ecological processes, and thus are intrinsically linked to rewilding. For example, the trophic complexity of a particular area may shape fire regimes via an influence on the quantity or arrangement of available fuel⁵². Additionally, human fire suppression could be considered a fifth switch: it does not influence fire ignition but plays a crucial role in determining whether fire spreads across the landscape.

Which switches play larger roles in constraining the type and frequency of fire regimes differs between environments. For example, fuel-limited ecosystems, like xeric shrublands⁵³, are typically hot and dry, but fire is constrained by biomass availability⁵⁴. In contrast, climate-limited ecosystems, like rainforests, have much available fuel but fire is constrained by high precipitation⁵⁵. Ultimately, switches shape fire events and regimes typically of different ecosystems and serve as anchor points for

rewilding actions⁵⁶. Climate-limited ecosystems, for example, will typically experience low frequency but high severity fire regimes²⁵.

Altered fire regimes

The climate influences all five switches and thus constrains the potential for rewilding approaches to restore fire regimes. For example, fuel availability is strongly influenced by long-term climate patterns that affect growth of vegetation⁵³, whereas short-term weather determines fuel dryness⁵⁷, the likelihood of lightning-occurrence⁵⁸, and the success of suppression efforts (Table 1)⁵⁹. As fire weather is related to long-term climate impacts on short-term weather patterns, global climate change is the primary driver of altered fire weather. Consequently, climate change mitigation is the only measure that can modify the likelihood of fire weather (Table 1)⁶⁰. Global climate change is also the largest modifier of the dryness of vegetation across the

landscape⁶¹, such as in the Brazilian Cerrado, where lower precipitation is predicted to increase fire frequency in some areas⁶². Climate change also affects the other switches, but there are still other factors that can influence these switches (Table 1).

This leaves four switches that can be influenced by local human actions in addition to climate: ignition, fuel availability, fuel dryness and fire suppression (Table 1). For fuel availability, actions such as land-use change can accumulate or reduce fuel, change its configuration and connectedness (e.g. its vertical and horizontal continuity) and the composition of plant communities, affecting the flammability of the fuel (Table 1). For fuel dryness, actions such as habitat fragmentation can influence the dryness or shading of the landscape, such as alterations to hydrology or modifications to accessible light (Table 1). For ignition, actions include changing the agent responsible (e.g. lightning versus human ignitions), as well as the frequency, season, spatial intensity and arrangement of ignition events (Table 1). Fire suppression, finally, can vary in its application, intensity and spatio-temporal distribution, further influencing fire dynamics (Table 1).

Marked anthropogenic changes in at least one of these five switches alter fire regimes and their ecological impacts (Table 1)³⁴, and do so differently across ecosystems. In fuel-limited ecosystems and in climate-limited ecosystems that historically experienced frequent human ignition, long-standing fire exclusion and suppression can increase the fuel available to burn, which subsequently increases the likelihood of high-severity fires (the ‘fire suppression paradox’; Table 1)^{63,64}. For example, in the fire-prone Canadian cordillera, Indigenous burning maintained a frequent and mixed-severity fire regime prior to colonization through patchy ignition of fire⁶⁵. However, human exclusion from forests and selective harvesting have altered fire regimes by reducing ignition frequency and pyro-diversity (i.e. homogenizing fire severity to high-severity events; Table 1)⁶⁵. In climate-limited systems, climate change is increasing fire frequency due to an increase in weather conditions suitable to carry fire across the landscape in combination with long-term climatic influence on vegetation moisture (Table 1)⁵⁵. For example, in boreal forests, climate change may double or even triple the frequency of fire within the century, due to the increase in days where local weather is suitable to carry fire⁶⁶. Thus, what an altered fire regime looks like, and the switches on which it depends, are context specific.

Altered fire regimes typically degrade ecosystems by changing biotic composition, vegetation structure and ecological function⁵². For example, in the historically fire-sensitive Amazonian rainforest, fire frequency and burnt area have increased dramatically, driven by deforestation, slash-and-burn practices and nearby pastoral burning^{67,68}. These altered fire regimes have shifted forest structure, abiotic conditions and ecosystem function, including altered species composition, canopy cover⁶⁹, evapotranspiration⁷⁰, chemical composition of the soil⁷¹, and reduced overall carbon stocks⁷². In addition, this has directly killed animals and plants, but also impacted them indirectly via habitat loss and fragmentation⁷³. Anthropogenic fire regimes in the Amazon may risk converting a primarily forested landscape to non-forest systems⁷⁴. In contrast, in fire-prone forests of the Mediterranean, land abandonment in combination with extensive active suppression of small wildfires has reduced the heterogeneity of fire mosaics in the last

50 years^{75,76}. Paradoxically, this has increased the likelihood of larger severe wildfires, due to a feedback loop created by the uniform development of fuel load, leading to more homogenized landscapes^{77,78}. While fire is an important driver of functional diversity in these fire-prone ecosystems, overly severe fire can kill soil biota and alter chemical composition⁷⁹, reduce the cover and composition of the vegetation⁸⁰, kill both canopy and soil-stored seed-banks^{81,82}, and facilitate invasion of woody species and fire feedback loops⁸³. Altered fire regimes are thus a risk to ecosystems, and approaches to restoring fire regimes are required.

Fire and other ecological processes in the rewilding framework

Understanding how fire interacts with other ecological processes is useful to develop pathways that strengthen these ecological processes to restore fire regimes. By identifying the connections between these processes, it is possible to design and develop rewilding actions, predict their ecological impacts, and apply them in context. Fire is intrinsically connected to two ecological processes that are central to rewilding: trophic complexity and dispersal (Figure 1)¹¹. Fire regimes can influence trophic complexity and dispersal, and vice versa they can affect fire regimes (Figure 1)⁸⁴. For example, herbivory and fire interact in complex ways, at times producing similar or opposing biotic responses, and competitive, deterministic or even antagonistic interactions^{85,86}. Fire may be functionally comparable to herbivory in its capacity to reduce biomass⁸⁷, and in this way fire and herbivory directly ‘compete’ for the same resource: vegetation, with differences in the types of vegetation they consume. Herbivores tend to select for low carbon-to-nitrogen ratios, due to the requirement for nutrient-dense food⁸⁸, whereas fire tends to select high carbon-to-nitrogen ratios, as drier fuel is more likely to burn^{89,90}. Herbivory can therefore reduce and change available fuel and thus co-determine fire risk^{91,92}, but only when flammable vegetation is also suitable food for herbivores^{88,93}.

Fire is an important influence on trophic complexity and trophic interactions (Figure 1). Fire can directly impact demographic processes by killing individuals⁹⁴ or promoting reproduction (e.g., fire-stimulated germination)⁹⁵. Fire patterns thus directly influence species occurrence, diversity, and thus trophic complexity. Fire also influences trophic complexity via mediating trophic interactions: facilitation, competition, parasitism, pathogenesis, mutualism, commensalism and predation (Figure 1)^{96–101}. For instance, fire can promote dietary and habitat resources (Figure 1)¹⁰², such as by stimulating the growth of young nutrient-rich plants that support herbivore foraging, or by increasing hunting habitats and prey abundance that support predator species such as the Golden Eagle (*Aquila chrysaetos*)¹⁰³. In return, trophic interactions influence the fire regime. For example, during predation, black kites (*Milvus migrans*) and brown falcons (*Falco berigora*) are known to ignite fire in savanna, by collecting burning plant material and dropping it elsewhere^{104,105}. Fire is thus intrinsically connected to trophic complexity and the interactions between species.

Fire can also influence dispersal, through fire evasion, by attracting species to post-fire environments¹⁰⁴, or by opening previously closed forest structures, allowing movement of large-bodied animals (Figure 1)¹⁰⁶. In contrast, fire can also prevent movement of species at lower trophic levels, if landscapes are

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Figure 1. Overview of the relationships between fire and trophic complexity and dispersal.

Fire influences trophic complexity through direct demographic processes but also through altering trophic interactions, such as commensalism and competition. In turn, trophic complexity influences fire through alteration of fuel and ignitions. Fire influences dispersal by mediating animal movements through the landscape. Dispersal influences fire through altering the connectivity of fuel. Together, trophic complexity, fire and dispersal alter species' functional, genetic and landscape diversity, which affect overall ecosystem functioning. (Images by Beth Macdonald, Aram, Cristofer Maximilian, Kenny Goossen, Dušan veverkolog, Vivek Kumar, Patti Black, Yuichi Kageyama, Mathew Schwartz, Ashish Upadhyay, Nick Fewings, Jan McCarthy, Alain Audet, and Erdenebayar, Unsplash/Pixabay; DNA image © Kadumago/Wikimedia Commons (CC BY 4.0).)

too open to allow sheltering from predators¹⁰⁷. The fire-related impact on dispersal thus also impacts trophic complexity, gene flow and genetic diversity¹⁰⁸. Dispersal can also alter fire regimes. Invasive plant species can increase the flammability of vegetation and initiate positive vegetation–fire feedbacks, such as the grass–fire cycle of Cheat Grass (*Bromus tectorum*) in North American sagebrush ecosystems, where the invasive species is favored by fire and grows dry and plentiful biomass quickly, thus promoting fire^{109,110}. Fire spread can also occur more easily if vegetation dispersal increases the continuity of vegetation⁴¹. In addition to the one-way relationships between the ecological processes, there are complex systemic interactions between fire, trophic complexity and dispersal, which in turn impacts alpha, beta, and gamma diversity (Figure 1). Re-wilding actions to restore fire regimes can therefore harness the relationships between fire, dispersal and trophic complexity to develop actions that achieve fire-related restoration goals.

Approaches to restoring fire regimes

To restore fire regimes, it is necessary to consider how to characterize what restored fire regimes look like, how to define targets of the restored fire regime, and how this relates to specific

ecosystems. It is also important to consider how to identify the kinds of indicators and attributes that help to maintain and adapt these targets in the context of other changing environmental drivers.

While we can observe the current patterns of fire regimes^{34,49,111}, defining what fire regimes should be restored to is more difficult. One possibility for defining target fire regimes for restoration might be to look to the past, characterizing previous fire regimes and their historical range of variation^{112,113}. This approach is particularly helpful for understanding the many changes to fire regimes, particularly within the last ~200 years (Table 1)³⁴. However, which historical timepoints should be used for restoration, and for what purpose? Megafauna extinctions had a profound effect on fire regimes around 15–20 thousand years ago^{114,115}, as did the first use of fire by *Homo erectus* and *Homo sapiens* several hundred thousand years ago^{116–120}. A second approach might be to define appropriate fire regimes using the ecological limits of contemporary species¹²¹. For example, using the fire-tolerance traits of trees to define the kinds of fire regimes that different ecosystems could tolerate¹²². The benefit of such an approach is it clearly links to the capacity of species to persist, but it also assumes that ecosystems and species assemblages are

Figure 2. Global diversity of fire across ecosystems.

Pink coloring shows the number of years in which fire occurred within each pixel, from white to dark pink (0–20 years, 1998–2018). The number of years a pixel was burnt was calculated using the ESA CCI ECV Fire Disturbance: D4.2.2 dataset^{218,219}, which displays burnt area on a monthly scale at a 0.05 degrees spatial resolution. Ecosystem Distributions use the dataset of indicative distribution maps for Ecosystem Functional Groups – Level 3 of IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology¹²³. (A) Global fire frequency from 1998–2018. (B) Fire frequency within the global distribution of trophic savannas (photo: savanna in the Serengeti by Hu Chen, Unsplash). (C) Fire frequency within the global distribution of sclerophyll hot deserts and semi-deserts (photo: spinifex semi-desert in Central Australia © Mark Marathon/Wikimedia Commons (CC BY-SA 4.0)). (D) Fire frequency within the global distribution of boreal and temperate high montane forests and woodlands (photo: Taiga in the Siberian mountains © Ninara/Wikimedia Commons (CC BY 2.0)).

unchanging. A third, ‘hands-off’ approach could be to let the changing climate set the future fire regime, within reason, assuming that it is adapted to the current context. However, under this approach, the fire regime is likely to be strongly influenced by an initial state of contemporary human influences, including species composition, fuel continuity, and ignitions, and, if unsupervised, may lead to undesirable and unacceptable socio-ecological outcomes.

We propose that a rewilding approach might learn from these past-, present-, and future-centered approaches to restore fire regimes. Such an approach might use the limits of important ecological processes themselves (within trophic complexity, dispersal and disturbance) to characterize the bounds of restored fire regimes. The benefit of focusing on ecological processes is the recognition that ecosystems are dynamic and thus may continue to transition toward abiotically and biotically ‘novel states’ (Box 1). It acknowledges that new fire regimes may be needed to maintain dynamic and self-sustaining ecosystems.

Target fire regimes could be approached by characterizing the types, dynamics and limits of processes that allow an ecosystem to be sustained and resilient to new challenges. This means identifying the key ecological processes and their influence on ecological function. These may include a range of processes related to trophic complexity, such as predation, herbivory, facilitation, mutualism, competition, pathogenesis and parasitism (Figure 1), each of which may include a range of forms and magnitudes of influence in the system. This may also include

dispersal, alongside other demographic processes (Figure 1). Characterizing these ecological processes and their relationship with ecosystem structure, species diversity functional diversity, and genetic diversity will help to identify their relevant importance in different ecosystems (Figure 1). In turn, this will help establish the fire regimes that sustain these ecological processes and thus

overall ecosystem function. Using this knowledge in tandem with societal context and goals will help to determine appropriate targets.

Which ecological processes are at play, and thus what target restored fire regimes will look like will vary in different ecosystems (Figure 2A). For example, in trophic savannas¹²³, fires occur yearly or bi-yearly under the strong impact of herbivores (Figure 2B)¹²⁴. The grasses in these ecosystems display adaptations that allow them to thrive under frequent fire and grazing, and benefit from a complex trophic structure¹²³. In contrast, sclerophyll hot deserts and semi-deserts typically burn in decadal cycles (Figure 2C). In these ecosystems, fire operates in ‘boom and bust’ climatic cycles, with short periods of high plant productivity supporting abundant life, and periodic fire releasing biomass and providing niches for other species⁸⁶. Different still are boreal and temperate high montane forests and woodlands, where fire occurs in multi-decadal to secular cycles (Figure 2D). The understory of these forests supports a diverse range of herbivores and predators, while large conifers dominate the upper canopy^{103,104}. In these ecosystems, fires dramatically change the forest structure, whereby mature trees give way to new recruits^{123,125}. As large trees take decades to mature, canopy fires need to be adequately spaced to allow trees to self-replace. Restoring fire regimes needs to align to the varying ways that ecological processes are expressed in different ecosystems to support a diverse range of species and communities.

A range of indicators and attributes can help to identify whether a fire regime is sustaining key ecological processes. This requires knowledge of how fire influences an ecosystem, which can be derived through a suite of traits and indices. For example, life-history traits, such as time to maturity, can help identify the fire frequency and severity that would enable reproduction and thus permit population maintenance^{126,127}. Proportion of mature individuals or reproductive output could thus be a useful indicator of whether fire frequency supports demographic processes. Another example is dispersal capacity: knowing how far species can disperse can help to understand the size of fires that support population persistence and related trophic interactions¹²⁸. Indicators can be derived for key trophic interactions, depending on what is essential to the function of different ecosystems. For example, if there is a commensalism between trees and tree-nesting species, the supply of hollow-bearing trees may be a useful indicator to assess the impact of frequency and severity of fire¹²⁹. Species diversity, functional diversity, and genetic diversity indices themselves may be useful to quantify the limits of the fire regime in supporting biodiversity and ecological function^{130,131}. For example, a biodiversity index may help identify the types of fire regimes that support a diverse community of species¹³¹. Different indicators selected to evidence the important ecological processes within an ecosystem, and the flow-on effects on biodiversity and ecosystem functioning, will help to determine whether fire regimes support complex, functioning ecosystems.

Utilizing indicators connected to ecological processes will also help to account for and adapt fire regime targets in relation to other environmental drivers. This requires identification of how fire regimes interact with other abiotic drivers. For example, decreased precipitation may reduce the speed of reproduction of key plant species, reducing the frequency of fire that would historically be suitable to support ecological processes and ecosystem resilience¹³². Land-use context may also influence the capacity for ecological processes, such as pollination, to cope with fire effects and thus influence the form of suitable fire regimes¹³³. Building an evidence base for ecological processes using future scenarios of climate, land-use, fire and biodiversity will be useful to forecast how these complex relationships may alter the existing limits of ecological processes to fire regimes¹³⁴. Nonetheless, simulating fire regimes is challenging, particularly under future scenarios, and further research effort is required to improve scenarios and models to support decision-making¹³⁵. Applying decision theory to this evidence base in the context of socio-ecological values will help to make decisions about how targets for fire regime restoration can be formed, adapted to novel conditions, and implemented to respond to the limits of ecological processes^{136,137}.

An important point in defining restored fire regimes is reconciling the extent of human agency and influence (Box 1)¹². People have introduced fire to ecosystems for millennia and have a long history of impacting trophic complexity and dispersal¹³⁸. For example, people's use of fire has shaped the diversity and structure of the savannas of Southern Mozambique for several hundred thousand years^{118,139}, and forest ecosystems of Lutruwita (Tasmania) for at least 40,000 years¹⁴⁰. Fire is often called "a global herbivore",⁸⁷ and thus human fire use could be compared

to herbivores reducing plant biomass. People's use of fire is also sometimes undertaken in the context of hunting practices (predation)¹⁴¹, and is important in promoting plant dispersal^{12,142}. People's use of fire is thus valuable to the maintenance of ecological processes and support of biodiversity, particularly in the context of an evolved history of pyrodiversity^{12,52,102,143}. Indeed, in some places, altered fire regimes and resulting changes to biodiversity are primarily linked to the exclusion of people from landscapes^{144,145}. For example, in the Klamath Mountains in Northern California, the exclusion of the Karuk Tribe and their cultural firing practices transformed fire regimes from regular, low severity and spatially stochastic to infrequent, high severity and spatially uniform fires^{144,146}. In our rewilding approach to fire regimes, we purposefully include people and their ecological function (Box 1) to restore ecological processes of trophic complexity, natural disturbance, and dispersal. Of course, people within a rewilding framework is not equivalent to intensive and severe pressure seen in the Anthropocene¹⁴⁷: rewilding fire, with humans or not, is aimed at the goal of restoring ecological processes to maintain functioning and dynamic ecosystems.

Characterizing the form and limits of key ecological processes within different ecosystems, inclusive of people, will help to build targets for fire regime restoration. Identifying indicators that connect to these ecological processes, and resulting ecosystem function, will help to adapt fire regime restoration targets across time, in the context of other changing abiotic drivers and socio-ecological values.

Potential rewilding actions for restoring fire regimes

Once target fire regimes are defined, rewilding actions can be selected based on the changes needed to support ecological function and depending on specific socio-ecological contexts. Rewilding can target the fire switches by pulling actionable levers with rewilding processes that support ecological function and reduce intensive anthropogenic pressure (Figure 3).

Fuel availability

Fuel availability can be reduced or re-arranged through rewilding through the recovery of herbivores (Figure 3)^{91,92,148}. That grazing herbivores reduce plant biomass is well established^{148,149}, such as with elk (*Cervus elaphus*) in Yellowstone National Park¹⁵⁰ and white rhinoceros (*Ceratotherium simum*) in Kruger National Park¹⁵¹. Browsing herbivores or mixed feeders, such as elephants, through their consumption of mid-story biomass, may also be useful for the reduction of vertical and horizontal fuel¹⁵², but most of the evidence comes from grazer species⁹¹. Landscapes where fuel has accumulated and increased the frequency and severity of fire beyond what the ecosystem can tolerate may benefit from herbivory. Similarly, in abandoned farmlands (Table 1), herbivory could be restored to reduce fuel loads and wildfire risk^{153,154}. Herbivory is also a relatively low-risk intervention for areas proximate to human housing and could be useful for reducing fuel availability in peri-urban areas. However, in some instances herbivory may promote woody encroachment¹⁵⁵, or the vegetation may not be favored as a food source by herbivores, demonstrating the importance of understanding the specific ecological communities. In this instance, rewilding through herbivory could be facilitated by first introducing fire and subsequently introducing herbivores. The

Figure 3. Possible rewilding actions for restoring fire regimes.

The switches that cannot be controlled through rewilding, the switches that can be influenced through rewilding, and some example rewilding actions related to these switches (images by Birger Strahl, Landon Parenteau, Keishpixl and Ylvers from Unsplash/Pixabay).

Fuel dryness

Fuel dryness can be altered locally through rewilding actions that impact hydrology, such as dam removal, restoration of ephemeral lakes, meandering rivers and flooding regimes, as well as animal reintroductions^{167,168}. For example, the re-introduction of aquatic ecosystem engineers, such as hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibius*), could widen river banks, create new river channels and alter hydrological flows¹⁶⁹. Changes in landscape hydrology as a result of ecosystem engineers can alter the patterns of fuel dryness and increase trophic complexity¹⁷⁰. In the Rocky

Mountains, beavers (*Castor canadensis*) dammed rivers, which reduced the intensity of fire, benefitting biodiversity and water quality¹⁷¹. However, these approaches are largely untested, and the efficacy and scalability of such actions are unknown.

For example, removal of artificial dams is likely to be effective in reducing local dryness through the restoration of natural hydrological cycles. However, dam removal may actually lower the available groundwater table, depending on the positioning of the dam¹⁷². Rewetting actions may also have interactions with fuel availability in some ecosystems, such as in arid grasslands, where periods of high water availability increase the primary productivity, producing booms of biomass that increase fuel availability¹⁷³. Fuel dryness can thus be targeted locally in some ecosystems and contexts, through rewilding actions that alter hydrological cycles whilst benefiting freshwater systems.

Ignition

Ignition can be targeted through the reduction, cessation or increase of human activity. Cessation of ignition is useful in fire-sensitive systems, where fire is currently too frequent or completely unnatural (Figure 3). Fire around and within these ecosystems can increase the openness of the canopy, change abiotic conditions, and alter species assemblages¹⁷⁴, and the patch edge is an important factor in ecosystem deterioration⁷⁰. For instance in the Luki Biosphere, a tropical rainforest in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, people have lit a surplus of fires in the last two decades and caused transitions from primary to secondary forests¹⁷⁵. However, in this area, fires are largely driven by a social dependence on slash and burn agriculture as a means of living¹⁷⁵, highlighting the need for an investment in participatory decision-making and incentivization if fire cessation is to be successful in many socio-ecological contexts.

initial fire could facilitate the growth of young shoots and recruits palatable to grazers who then prevent the accumulation of biomass^{22,124,156}.

Rewilding can also change fuel availability through the re-introduction of ecosystem engineers, carnivores, or plant species (Figure 3). Carnivore reintroduction may be effective to reduce the pressure of herbivores and accumulate biomass in ecosystems that have experienced an unnatural decline in fire frequency¹⁵⁷. However, the success of carnivores in lowering herbivory pressure is limited for large-bodied herbivores¹⁵⁸, and carnivores are likely to cause human–wildlife conflicts in populated areas. Ecosystem engineers can also be used to disturb and disconnect fuel when digging, trampling or foraging, such as the European wild boar (*Sus scrofa*)¹⁵⁹ and the Mallee Fowl (*Leipoa ocellata*) of South-eastern Australia^{160,161}. Digging animals also support survival during fires, by providing refugia^{162,163}. Fuel availability may also be altered by the introduction or reintroduction of plant species, which can change the flammability of the vegetation. For example, in the grasslands of southern New Zealand, the invasion of exotic rosette-forming forbs decreased flammability¹⁶⁴. This may decrease the frequency and intensity of the extant fire regime, which has been driven by burning from Māori and European settler communities¹⁶⁵ and could potentially lead to positive feedbacks that change the plant composition of grasslands¹⁶⁴. Conversely, reduced flammability could also aid native flora that generally lack fire-adapted traits necessary to cope with climate-driven changes to the fire regime. Allowing novel species communities to assemble could reduce the intensity and spatial continuity of events. However, the opposite may also be true, as invasion by flammable grasses and understory plants can increase fire risk significantly¹⁶⁶, highlighting the need to consider the interactions between ecological processes when targeting fuel availability with rewilding actions.

Figure 4. Four key steps to restoring fire regimes through rewilding. We propose that the first step to restoring fire regimes is to characterize the dynamics and limits of ecological processes within an area. The second step is to identify altered and target regimes based on these ecological processes, and to select restorative target switches based on these. The third step is to implement rewilding actions based on these switches that are aimed at strengthening key ecological processes integral to the ecosystem. Finally, monitoring and evaluating success enables adaptive management in the face of ongoing changes to the environment and socio-ecological context.

In fire-prone areas, ignition can be rewilded from intensive pressures by adapting frequencies, spatial densities, and seasons, to create pyrodiversity, defined by fine-scale mosaics of different fire ages^{28,102,176}. For example, many Indigenous groups globally light fires, and these techniques can substantially increase biodiversity and ecosystem function^{177–181}. In Martu country (North West Australia), fire is applied across the landscape in heterogenous patches, in a localized practice of people reading Country and hunting Goanna (*Varanus gouldii*)¹⁴¹. Fires are lit earlier in the colder months at lower intensity and patchier consistency, preventing high intensity lightning-ignited wildfires from occurring later in the hot and dry season, which in turn promotes more heterogeneity and stochasticity in the landscape, including long-unburnt patches^{141,182}. Pyrodiversity, as a result of Martu fire practices, increases the richness and diversity of plant species within the landscape¹⁸³ and aids in seed dispersal¹⁴². Localized use of fire that promotes fine-scale pyrodiversity is distinct from mechanized ignitions, which are often planned as total area-based targets at multi-year cycles, requiring centralized efforts from management agencies to travel to apply fire with accelerants at high spatial densities and over large areas (e.g. petrol torches, aerial ignitions), and are often paired with suppression efforts¹⁸⁴. Localized firing practices require specific expertise and an ongoing relationship between

people and place across time¹⁸⁵, not to mention a political landscape that supports and permits individuals to light fires where they are, as they see fit¹⁸⁶. This makes implementation challenging in many areas. Conversely, this may be a useful opportunity in places that are most difficult to rewild — where people live — where fire is often starved^{187,188} and where there is the highest risk of losing lives and properties to intense wildfire¹⁸⁹. This would require significant initial effort to foster expertise, relationship to land, and changes to perception and legislation of fire risk, among other challenges.

Suppression

Suppression can be rewilded through reducing the intensity and changing the arrangement of suppression activities, including allowing naturally ignited wildfires to burn (Figure 3). This may be useful for areas that have experienced a decline in fire frequency, but an increase in high severity fires, or where historical anthropogenic ignition practices have been excluded⁶³. For example, in Yosemite National Park, after over a century of fire suppression, a controlled wildfire policy allowed wildfires to continue to burn with consideration of life and property^{190,191}. The resulting reintroduction of a more frequent, mixed-severity fire regime reduced the density of overly dense forests, increased heterogeneity of tree sizes, opened the tree canopy and reduced forest cover by one quarter^{192–194}. This has increased trophic complexity through the appearance of shrubland and meadow species, and has produced associated benefits including increased water flow and storage^{190,195}. Reducing fire suppression activities where possible may be a particularly resource-effective decision, as fires become increasingly more difficult to suppress under climate change⁵⁹. Nonetheless, there are areas where reducing intensive fire suppression may be difficult or socially unacceptable, such as close to human settlements.

Pathways to rewilding fire

Evidence is emerging that rewilding has the potential to restore fire regimes and related ecological processes, but much remains to be explored, tested and documented. Using decision theory and focusing on context-specific goals can help to mitigate unintended consequences (Figure 4). For example, passive rewilding or land abandonment can have negative consequences¹⁹⁶, as fuel loads may accumulate¹⁹⁷. It also may entail other negative ecological consequences, such as facilitating the arrival of invasive species⁸³. However, if increased fire frequency is the intended outcome, such as if target areas lack biomass, and seed stores are proximate, passive rewilding could be useful. Similarly, reducing suppression may be a favorable option for fire-prone areas that have experienced a reduction in fire frequency, such as temperate pyric sclerophyll forests and woodlands (Figure 5A). In these ecosystems, reducing the suppression of smaller fires may benefit ecological function while decreasing the risk of hotter fires. However, reducing fire suppression would be inappropriate for fire-sensitive ecosystems, such as tropical rainforests, where fire should be limited, and singular un-suppressed fires may represent transformations to novel ecosystem states⁷⁰.

We propose that, first, before restoring fire, the types and magnitudes of ecological processes should first be characterized (Figure 4). For example, in ecologically functioning boreal forests, there is a dominance of large conifers, some smaller

A Example: Temperate pyric sclerophyll forests and woodlands

Characterize

Open evergreen tree canopies. Diverse plants, birds, and invertebrates. Low productivity and periodic droughts limit the animals at higher trophic levels. Some mammalian herbivores specialise in consumption of high fibre content. Plants exhibit fire dependencies and tolerances and benefit from fire-regulated competitive release.

Suppression

Restore

Reduce the intensity and spatial coverage of suppression

Rewild

Allow smaller wildfires to burn without suppression, reducing the likelihood of larger, high-intensity wildfires, and increasing stochasticity in the spatial footprint of fire.

B Example: Boreal forest

Characterize

Herbivores and predators move widely, dominance of large conifers, some smaller trees, lichen and moss, periodic stochastic disturbance by insects or fires dramatically change the forest structure.

Fuel availability

Restore

Reduce available fuel and connectedness

Rewild

Promote and/or reintroduce herbivore populations to increase herbivory of mid-story species.

Current Biology

Figure 5. Using the key steps in example ecosystems.

(A) Using the steps outlined in Figure 4 in an example temperate pyric and sclerophyll forest and woodland ecosystem. (B) Using the steps outlined in Figure 4 in an example boreal forest ecosystem. (Images by Hans Veth, Diana Parkhouse, Ma Ti, Arno Ryser, Zdeněk Macháček, Odile Luna, Mission Pilot, Cédric Le Bars, Markus Kammermann, Juho Luomala, Juho Luomala, Abbass Zahreddine, Kenny Goossen, Debabrata Patra and Jaap Straydog and from Unsplash.)

frequency of fire¹⁹⁹. Climate change plays a clear role in all four switches and determines fire weather entirely. There is a possibility that climate change will alter these switches beyond what rewilding actions are capable of influencing, particularly via changes to fire weather^{200–203}. Nonetheless, rewilding fire may also be an opportunity to mitigate or reduce expected climate change impacts. Second, climate change is also altering the biotic responses of species to fire regimes²⁰⁴. There is a possibility that the historical tolerance of organisms to fire regimes may be reduced. This highlights the

importance of recognizing the need to embrace dynamic, novel ecosystems and fire regimes in a novel biosphere. Ongoing monitoring and evaluation, and careful testing of biotic responses to novel interventions, will be important tools to facilitate evidence-based decision-making as the climate and landscape change. Third, fire occurs in a suite of multiple intersecting disturbances, and care should be taken to identify the complex interactions between fire events and other disturbances within different ecosystems. Finally, wildfire poses an inherent risk to human life and property¹⁸⁹. We reason that rewilding fire can, in many cases, help to mitigate some of the risks that altered fire regimes pose to people. Nonetheless, as has been identified in trophic rewilding approaches, proactive policies for rewilding may face local resistance or political inertia, particularly those seeking to increase the frequency of fire near human settlements. This resistance is partially fed by the unknowns that currently still surround the topic of fire and rewilding. Participatory decision-making or, at least, active consultation with local communities will be essential to rewild fire in an equitable and inclusive manner.

Further work on the role of rewilding in restoring fire regimes is needed. Explicit testing of components of the framework within various ecological and societal contexts and specific accompanying goals is essential. There are few concrete examples that carefully test and document the effectiveness of intentionally manipulating fire regimes to improve and sustain biodiversity, and progressing these tests is integral to advancement. We reason the framework developed here will be useful to guide future fire-related rewilding actions and contribute to global targets that seek to restore ecosystems, protect biodiversity, and conserve related ecosystem services.

Challenges and opportunities for rewilding fire regimes

There are several challenges to restoring fire regimes through rewilding, some of which we have detailed above. First, climate change is already altering the size, severity, seasonality and

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DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

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